

Supplementary Material: HAC-ODT: Online Decision Transformer Optimization through Historical Action Guidance and Context-Aware Q-Value Correction

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1 Additional Experimental Results

As shown in Figure 1, our algorithm achieves consistent performance improvements over the ODT+TD3 baseline across all 12 D4RL MuJoCo continuous control environments, covering medium, medium-replay and random datasets with varying data quality. Furthermore, our algorithm exhibits significantly better training stability than ODT+TD3, especially in sensitive high-dimensional environments such as Hopper, where the fluctuation magnitude of our method is drastically reduced compared to the baseline.

As shown in Figure 2, our HAC-ODT also achieves significant and consistent performance gains over the baseline across all 6 D4RL AntMaze navigation benchmarks, ranging from simple short-range umaze scenarios to challenging long-horizon large-scale navigation tasks. Our method shows a more prominent advantage in complex large-scale AntMaze environments, with significantly faster convergence speed, higher final normalized score, and smoother learning curves than ODT+TD3.

2 Proofs

We provide detailed proofs for two key claims in the main paper: the consistency between Q-value and RTG in Section 3.3, and the validity of the Context-Aware Q-Value Correction Loss in Section 3.4. All notations are consistent with the main paper (see Section 2.1 for MDP fundamentals, Section 2.2 for TD3 definitions, and Section 2.3 for DT definitions).

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Fig. 1. Performance Comparison of HAC-ODT and ODT+TD3 on Standard D4RL MuJoCo Benchmarks.

Fig. 2. Performance Comparison of HAC-ODT and ODT+TD3 on D4RL AntMaze Navigation Benchmarks.

2.1 Equivalence Proof of Q-Value and RTG

Definition 1 (RTG). For a trajectory $\tau = (s_1, a_1, r_1, \dots, s_T, a_T, r_T)$, the RTG at step t is defined as:

$$RTG_t = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\sum_{i=t}^T r_i \right]$$

where T is the terminal step of τ .

Definition 2 (Q-Value in TD3). For a deterministic policy $\pi : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ (adopted by HAC-ODT), the Q-value of state-action pair (s_t, a_t) satisfies the Bellman optimality equation:

$$Q_{\theta_j}(s_t, a_t) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} [r_t + \gamma \cdot Q_{\theta_j}(s_{t+1}, \pi(s_{t+1}))]$$

where Q_{θ_j} denotes the j -th Critic network in TD3 ($j = 1, 2$), \mathcal{D} is the replay buffer, $r_t = R(s_t, a_t)$ is the immediate reward, $\gamma \in [0, 1)$ is the discount factor, $\pi(s_{t+1})$ is the deterministic action output by HAC-ODT for next state s_{t+1} .

Lemma 1 (Q-Value Expansion). The Q-value can be expanded to the cumulative future reward expectation by continuously expanding $Q_{\theta_j}(s_{t+1}, \pi(s_{t+1}))$:

$$Q_{\theta_j}(s_t, a_t) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\sum_{i=t}^T \gamma^{i-t} r_i \right]$$

where T is the terminal step of the trajectory.

Proof (Proof of Lemma 1). We prove the expansion by mathematical induction on the step t :

Base Case ($t = T$): At the terminal step T , there are no future states (s_{T+1} is undefined), so the Bellman equation in Definition 2 simplifies to:

$$Q_{\theta_j}(s_T, a_T) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} [r_T + \gamma \cdot 0] = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} [r_T]$$

The cumulative reward form at $t = T$ is $\sum_{i=T}^T \gamma^{i-T} r_i = r_T$, so the base case holds.

Inductive Step: Assume the expansion holds for step $t + 1$:

$$Q_{\theta_j}(s_{t+1}, \pi(s_{t+1})) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\sum_{i=t+1}^T \gamma^{i-(t+1)} r_i \right]$$

Substitute this into the Bellman equation for step t (Definition 2):

$$Q_{\theta_j}(s_t, a_t) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[r_t + \gamma \cdot \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\sum_{i=t+1}^T \gamma^{i-(t+1)} r_i \right] \right]$$

By linearity of expectation, the nested expectation reduces to a single expectation over \mathcal{D} . Adjust the discount factor exponent: $\gamma \cdot \gamma^{i-(t+1)} = \gamma^{i-t}$. Thus:

$$Q_{\theta_j}(s_t, a_t) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[r_t + \sum_{i=t+1}^T \gamma^{i-t} r_i \right] = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\sum_{i=t}^T \gamma^{i-t} r_i \right]$$

The inductive step holds. Combining the base case and inductive step, the expansion is proven for all $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$.

Theorem 1 (Semantic Equivalence). *Q-value and RTG are semantically equivalent: both represent the cumulative future reward from the current, and their optimization objectives are identical.*

Proof (Proof of Theorem 1). First, we establish the core semantic alignment between Q-value and RTG by analyzing their fundamental definitions. By Definition 1, the $\text{RTG}_t = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\sum_{i=t}^T r_i \right]$ directly quantifies the total undiscounted future reward obtainable from step t to the terminal step T .

In contrast, Lemma 1 shows the $Q_{\theta_j}(s_t, a_t) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\sum_{i=t}^T \gamma^{i-t} r_i \right]$ is the expected weighted sum of future rewards over the same time horizon. The discount factor γ serves exclusively as a coefficient to adjust the relative weight of near-term versus long-term rewards—for instance. So both RTG and Q-value are designed to assess the cumulative future reward.

Furthermore, when the discount factor is set to $\gamma = 1$, the expanded Q-value form simplifies to:

$$Q_{\theta_j}(s_t, a_t) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\sum_{i=t}^T 1^{i-t} r_i \right] = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\sum_{i=t}^T r_i \right].$$

Substituting the definition of RTG (Definition 1) into this expression yields:

$$Q_{\theta_j}(s_t, a_t) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}}[\text{RTG}_t].$$

This result confirms that RTG is a special case of the Q-value, while the Q-value represents a generalized form of RTG that accommodates flexible weighting of future rewards via γ .

2.2 Proof of Validity of Context-Aware Q-Value Correction Loss

The Context-Aware Q-Value Correction Loss \mathcal{L}_{QC} is designed to mitigate policy bias in Q-value estimation caused by exploration noise. We formally prove that minimizing \mathcal{L}_{QC} reduces the gap between Q-values of deterministic policy actions (from HAC-ODT) and noisy environment-interaction actions, thereby correcting policy bias.

Definition 3 (\mathcal{L}_{QC}). For a trajectory segment $\tau' = (s_{t-K+1}, a_{t-K+1}^{noisy}, \dots, s_t, a_t^{noisy})$ with context length K , \mathcal{L}_{QC} is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{QC} = \mathbb{E}_{\tau' \in \mathcal{D}} \left[\frac{1}{K-1} \sum_{j=1,2} \sum_{i=t-K+1}^{t-1} \|\Delta Q_j - r_i\|_2^2 \right]$$

where $\Delta Q_j = Q_{\theta_j}(s_i, a_i^{noisy}) - \gamma \cdot Q_{\theta_j}(s_{i+1}, a_{i+1}^{noisy})$, Q_{θ_j} is the j -th Critic network in TD3, and a_i^{noisy} is the environment-interaction action with exploration noise from the replay buffer.

Definition 4 (Policy Bias). Policy bias arises when the deterministic HAC-ODT policy outputs a noise-free action $a_{i+1}^{det} = \pi^{HAC-ODT}(s_{i+1})$ that differs from the noisy environment-interaction action a_{i+1}^{noisy} (collected during exploration with injected noise). It leads to a gap between the Q -values of the deterministic and noisy actions:

$$Q_j^{Bias} = Q_{\theta_j}(s_{i+1}, a_{i+1}^{det}) - Q_{\theta_j}(s_{i+1}, a_{i+1}^{noisy})$$

Our goal is to show that minimizing \mathcal{L}_{QC} reduces $|Q_j^{Bias}|$.

Theorem 2 (Validity of \mathcal{L}_{QC}). Minimizing \mathcal{L}_{QC} effectively reduces the policy bias Q_j^{Bias} , as $\Delta Q_j - r_i$ is linearly proportional to Q_j^{Bias} .

Proof. From TD3’s target Q -value definition in Equation 1 and the Bellman equation in Definition 2, the converged Q -value satisfies:

$$Q_{\theta_j}(s_i, a_i) \approx \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[r_i + \gamma \cdot Q_{\theta_j}(s_{i+1}, a_{i+1}^{pred}) \right]$$

Rearranging terms and substituting $\Delta Q_j = Q_{\theta_j}(s_i, a_i) - \gamma \cdot Q_{\theta_j}(s_{i+1}, a_{i+1})$:

$$\Delta Q_j - r_i \approx \gamma \cdot \left(Q_{\theta_j}(s_{i+1}, a_{i+1}^{pred}) - Q_{\theta_j}(s_{i+1}, a_{i+1}) \right)$$

By Definition 4, the right-hand side is exactly $\gamma \cdot Q_j^{Bias}$. Thus:

$$\Delta Q_j - r_i \approx \gamma \cdot Q_j^{Bias}$$

Squaring both sides and taking the expectation (consistent with the MSE formulation of \mathcal{L}_{QC}):

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\|\Delta Q_j - r_i\|_2^2 \right] \approx \gamma^2 \cdot \mathbb{E} \left[\|Q_j^{Bias}\|_2^2 \right]$$

This shows that \mathcal{L}_{QC} is proportional to the expected squared policy bias. Minimizing \mathcal{L}_{QC} therefore directly reduces $\mathbb{E} \left[\|Q_j^{Bias}\|_2^2 \right]$, verifying the validity of the context-aware Q -value correction loss.

Remark 1. The proportionality factor γ ensures that the correction focuses on near-term policy bias, which has a more significant impact on cumulative rewards. This aligns with the design of \mathcal{L}_{QC} to leverage long-sequence contextual information while prioritizing critical near-term corrections. Additionally, since \mathcal{L}_{QC} is added to original loss of TD3, it preserves TD3’s ability to estimate long-term returns while mitigating policy bias.

2.3 Proof of Effectiveness of Historical Action Guidance Loss

\mathcal{L}_{HA} leverages high-value historical actions retrieved from the high-quality O2O dataset to guide HAC-ODT’s policy optimization. We prove its effectiveness by verifying its ability to enhance the policy’s expected Q-value and the validity of the adaptive weight w_t .

Definition 5 (\mathcal{L}_{HA}). For a trajectory segment $\tau' = (s_{t-K+1}, a_{t-K+1}, \dots, s_t, a_t)$ with context length K , \mathcal{L}_{HA} is a MSE-based imitation loss targeting high-value historical actions a_t^{history} :

$$\mathcal{L}_{HA} = \mathbb{E}_{\tau' \in \mathcal{D}} \left[\frac{1}{K} \sum_{i \in \tau'} \left\| \pi^{\text{HAC-ODT}}(s_i) - a_i^{\text{history}} \right\|_2^2 \right]$$

where, a_i^{history} is historical action retrieved from the high-quality O2O dataset $\mathcal{D}_{\text{high}}$, satisfying $Q_{\theta_1}(s_i, a_i^{\text{history}}) > Q_{\theta_1}(s_i, a_i)$, $\pi^{\text{HAC-ODT}}(s_i)$ is action predicted by HAC-ODT for state s_i , $w_t = \sigma \left(\delta \cdot \mathbb{E}_{i \in \tau'} \left[Q_{\theta_1}(s_i, a_i^{\text{history}}) - Q_{\theta_1}(s_i, a_i) \right] \right)$ is an adaptive weight, with $\sigma(\cdot)$ as the sigmoid function and δ as the scaling factor.

Theorem 3 (Expected RTG Enhancement). Minimizing \mathcal{L}_{HA} increases the expected RTG of HAC-ODT policy $\pi^{\text{HAC-ODT}}$.

Proof. The optimization objective of \mathcal{L}_{HA} is:

$$\min \mathcal{L}_{HA} \iff \min \mathbb{E}_{\tau' \in \mathcal{D}} \left[\frac{1}{K} \sum_{i \in \tau'} \left\| \pi_{\phi}^{\text{HAC-ODT}}(s_i) - a_i^{\text{history}} \right\|_2^2 \right]$$

where a_i^{history} is the high-value historical action retrieved from the high-quality O2O dataset $\mathcal{D}_{\text{high}}$.

By the semantic equivalence of Q-value and RTG (Theorem 1), the Q-value superiority condition $Q_{\theta_1}(s_i, a_i^{\text{history}}) > Q_{\theta_1}(s_i, a_i)$ directly translates to RTG superiority:

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\text{RTG}_i \mid a_i = a_i^{\text{history}} \right] > \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\text{RTG}_i \mid a_i = a_i \right]$$

This is because both Q-value and RTG quantify the cumulative future reward, differing only in discount weighting.

Minimizing \mathcal{L}_{HA} reduces the distance between $\pi^{\text{HAC-ODT}}(s_i)$ and a_i^{history} , meaning $\pi^{\text{HAC-ODT}}(s_i)$ converges to a_i^{history} as \mathcal{L}_{HA} approaches zero. As a result, the expected RTG of the policy’s output action aligns with the higher RTG of a_i^{history} :

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\text{RTG}_t \mid a_t = \pi^{\text{HAC-ODT}}(s_t) \right] \rightarrow \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{D}} \left[\text{RTG}_t \mid a_t = a_t^{\text{history}} \right]$$

Since a_t^{history} has a higher expected RTG than the original action a_t , minimizing \mathcal{L}_{HA} directly increases the expected RTG of HAC-ODT’s policy, confirming the effectiveness of the loss in guiding the policy toward higher cumulative future rewards.

3 Experimental Details

3.1 Environments

We evaluated our dataset on four widely used MuJoCo locomotion environments: Hopper, HalfCheetah, Walker2d, and Ant. Detailed descriptions of each environment are as follows:

- **Hopper**: A 2D locomotion task where the agent controls a one-legged robot to hop forward. Its state is 11-dimensional, describing the joint coordinates and velocities of the robot. The action space is 3-dimensional, representing the torques applied to the three joints at each step.
- **HalfCheetah**: A 2D locomotion task where the agent controls a cheetah-like robot to run forward. Its state is 17-dimensional, including joint coordinates and velocities. The action space is 6-dimensional, representing the torques applied to the six joints at each step.
- **Walker2d**: A 2D locomotion task where the agent controls an bipedal robot to walk forward. Its state is 17-dimensional, describing joint angles and velocities. The action space is 6-dimensional, representing the torques applied to the 6 DoF joints at each step.
- **Ant**: A 3D locomotion task where the agent controls a quadrupedal ant robot to walk in a 3D environment. Its state is 111-dimensional, describing joint coordinates and velocities. The action space is 8-dimensional, representing the torques applied to the 8 DoF joints at each step.
- **AntMaze**: A challenging long-horizon navigation task extended from the Maze2D benchmark, where the agent controls a quadrupedal Ant robot to navigate through a maze and reach the target state. Its state space is 27-dimensional, and the action space is 8-dimensional.

3.2 Datasets

MuJoCo Locomotion Datasets For MuJoCo tasks, We evaluate our method on three datasets of varying quality: *medium*, *medium-replay*, and *random*.

- ***medium* datasets**: Consist of trajectories collected by agents trained via reinforcement learning, which were stopped early to maintain a moderate performance level.
- ***medium-replay* datasets**: Contain trajectories sampled from the replay buffers of agents mentioned above during their training process.
- ***random* datasets**: Comprise trajectories collected by agents following a random policy.

Table 1 presents the size and the normalized reward of the data in each MuJoCo dataset.

Dataset	Size	Normalized Reward
Hopper-medium-v2	999906	44.32 \pm 12.27
Hopper-medium-replay-v2	402000	14.98 \pm 16.32
Hopper-random-v2	999996	1.19 \pm 1.16
HalfCheetah-medium-v2	1000000	40.68 \pm 5.12
HalfCheetah-medium-replay-v2	202000	27.17 \pm 15.79
HalfCheetah-random-v2	1000000	0.07 \pm 2.90
Walker2d-medium-v2	999995	62.09 \pm 23.83
Walker2d-medium-replay-v2	302000	14.84 \pm 19.48
Walker2d-medium-random-v2	999997	0.01 \pm 0.09
Ant-medium-v2	999946	80.30 \pm 35.82
Ant-medium-replay-v2	302000	30.95 \pm 31.66
Ant-medium-random-v2	999930	6.36 \pm 10.07

Table 1. The size and the average and standard deviation of the normalized reward of the datasets from D4RL MuJoCo used in our experiments.

Dataset	Size	Normalized Reward
Antmaze-Umaze-v2	998573	86.14 \pm 34.55
Antmaze-Umaze-Diverse-v2	999000	3.48 \pm 18.32
Antmaze-Medium-Play-v2	999000	90.85 \pm 28.83
Antmaze-Medium-Diverse-v2	999000	66.29 \pm 47.27
Antmaze-Large-Play-v2	999000	92.73 \pm 25.97
Antmaze-Large-Diverse-v2	999000	86.17 \pm 34.52

Table 2. The size and the average and standard deviation of the normalized reward of the AntMaze datasets from D4RL used in our experiments.

AntMaze Navigation Datasets For AntMaze tasks, we use the 6 standard offline datasets provided by D4RL: Umaze, Umaze-Diverse, Medium-Play, Medium-Diverse, Large-Play and Large-Diverse. The terms Umaze, Medium and Large describe the scale of the maze, while Diverse and Play denote the dataset type. Diverse means the agent’s starting point and target are randomly generated in the offline dataset, while Play means the target is predefined via handcrafted design. The base Umaze environment is the simplest scenario with fixed starting point and target.

Table 2 presents the size and the normalized reward of the data in each MuJoCo dataset.

Following the common practice in IQL and CQL, we apply reward shaping for all AntMaze environments: we subtract 1 from all rewards in both the offline dataset and online environment during the training of our method and all baselines, to provide a denser reward signal for sparse-reward navigation tasks. Notably, we use the original sparse reward to calculate the final normalized score for fair performance comparison.

Environment	Random Score ($\mathcal{R}_{\text{random}}$)	Expert Score ($\mathcal{R}_{\text{expert}}$)
Hopper	-20.272305	3234.3
HalfCheetah	-280.178953	12135.0
Walker2d	1.629008	4592.3
Ant	-325.6	3879.7
AntMaze	0	1

Table 3. Predefined D4RL reference scores for the MuJoCo locomotion environments used in our experiments.

3.3 Metrics

The D4RL normalized score is a core metric for the unified evaluation of task performance in the field of offline reinforcement learning. It maps raw reward values to a standard range via a min-max normalization formula, which greatly simplifies performance comparisons across different tasks and algorithms. The formal definition of the D4RL normalized score is given by:

$$\text{Normalized Score} = 100 \times \frac{\mathcal{R}_{\text{agent}} - \mathcal{R}_{\text{random}}}{\mathcal{R}_{\text{expert}} - \mathcal{R}_{\text{random}}} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{R}_{\text{random}}$ denotes the average undiscounted return of a random policy over 100 episodes in the same environment, $\mathcal{R}_{\text{expert}}$ represents the average undiscounted return of a converged RL algorithm after extensive online fine-tuning over 100 episodes in the same environment, $\mathcal{R}_{\text{agent}}$ denotes the return of the agent.

Notably, D4RL fixes the values of $\mathcal{R}_{\text{random}}$ and $\mathcal{R}_{\text{expert}}$ for each environment in a predefined manner, with the specific reference scores for our experimental environments summarized in Table 3. For AntMaze navigation tasks, since the reward signal is extremely sparse (only provided upon reaching the goal), the normalized score is defined as the success rate averaged over multiple parallel test environments, and its maximum possible value is thus capped at 100. For MuJoCo locomotion tasks, a normalized score exceeding 100 indicates that the performance of the current algorithm is superior to the online RL algorithm used for dataset construction, and a higher normalized score corresponds to better algorithm performance.

4 Hyperparameters

Table 4 summarizes the general hyperparameters shared across all environments, and Table 5 reports the environment-specific hyperparameters that vary across different tasks. For hyperparameters that are also employed in the ODT+TD3 algorithm, we strictly adopt its original hyperparameter configurations. But for the pre-defined target RTG, RTG_{eval} and $\text{RTG}_{\text{online}}$, we set them to 110% of the average return of the current algorithm upon convergence, which allows for more rational guidance of the ODT network. When running the ODT+TD3 baseline, we initialize β , ζ to 0, θ to 1.

Hyperparam	Value
dim of embedding dimensions	512
dim of attention heads per layer	4
dim of transformer layers	4
Dropout	0.1
Actor Optimizer	LAMB [68]
steps collected per epoch	≥ 1000 (random dataset), 1 trajectory (others)
Actor activation function	ReLU
Scheduler	10^4 steps, linear warmup
Critic layer	2
Critic width	256
Critic activation function	ReLU
γ	0.99
Batch size	256
actor update per epoch	300
Online exploration noise	0.1
Replay buffer size	1K
TD3 policy noise	0.2
TD3 noise clip	0.5
TD3 target update ratio	0.005

Table 4. The common hyperparameters across all environments used in our experiments. γ is the discount factor in Section 2.1.

Environment	T_{train}	T_{eval}	RTG_{eval}	$\text{RTG}_{\text{online}}$	Pretrain	α	Online α	lr_c	lr_a	Weight decay	#pretrain steps	β	θ	ζ
Ho-M-v2	20	5	3600	7200	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	0.0005	5K	5	0.7	0.5
Ho-MR-v2	20	5	3600	7200	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	0.0005	5K	5	0.7	0.5
Ho-R-v2	20	5	3600	7200	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	0.0005	5K	5	0.7	0.5
Ha-M-v2	20	5	10000	12000	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	5K	5	0.7	0.3
Ha-MR-v2	20	5	10000	12000	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	5K	5	0.7	0.3
Ha-R-v2	20	5	10000	12000	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	5K	5	0.7	0.3
Wa-M-v2	20	5	6000	6000	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-3}	10^{-3}	10K	5	0.7	0.5
Wa-MR-v2	20	5	6000	6000	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-3}	10^{-3}	10K	5	0.7	0.5
Wa-R-v2	20	5	6000	6000	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-3}	10^{-3}	10K	5	0.7	0.5
An-M-v2	20	1	6000	6000	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	5K	5	0.7	0.5
An-MR-v2	20	1	6000	6000	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	5K	5	0.7	0.5
An-R-v2	20	1	6000	6000	0	0.1	0.1	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	5K	5	0.7	0.5
AnM-U-v2	5	1	-100	-100	0.1	0.1	0.1	2×10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	40K	5	0.7	0.5
AnM-UD-v2	5	1	-100	-100	0.1	0.1	0.1	2×10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	40K	5	0.7	0.5
AnM-MP-v2	5	1	-200	-200	0.1	0.1	0.1	2×10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	200K	5	0.7	0.5
AnM-MD-v2	5	1	-200	-200	0.1	0.1	0.1	2×10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	200K	5	0.7	0.5
AnM-LP-v2	5	1	-500	-500	0.1	0.1	0.1	2×10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	200K	5	0.7	0.5
AnM-LD-v2	5	1	-500	-500	0.1	0.1	0.1	2×10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	200K	5	0.7	0.5

Table 5. Environment-specific hyperparameters, where T_{train} and T_{eval} denote training and evaluation context lengths, RTG_{eval} and $\text{RTG}_{\text{online}}$ represent RTG during evaluation and online rollout respectively, α is the coefficient for RL gradient, lr_c is the critic learning rate, lr_a is the actor learning rate, β is the parameter for balancing the importance of states and actions, θ is the proportion of trajectories removed from the replay buffer, ζ is the hyperparameter for the context-aware Q-value correction loss.

5 Computational Resources

All experiments are conducted on an Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS server, using a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPU (from two available) and a 32-core 13th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-13900K CPU @ 3.00GHz. D4RL MuJoCo experiments take approximately 9 to 12 hours to complete, with the time bottleneck residing in gradient updates, about 50% of the total training time is consumed by backpropagation and parameter updating. Compared with ODT+TD3, the construction of a high-quality O2O dataset in our method, together with the introduction of the historical action-guided loss and context-based Q-value correction loss, leads to an approximate 10% increase in training time. Nevertheless, our algorithm yields markedly better performance. From this perspective, the incurred time overhead is well acceptable.